

Big Data Analytics Implementation Risks Conceptual Model

Tshegofatso Evidence Hutang¹[0000-1111-2222-3333] and Ignitia Motjoloane²[1111-2222-3333-4444]

¹ Tshwane University Of Technology, Pretoria, SA
HutangTE@tut.ac.za

² North West University, Mahikeng, SA
ignitia.motjoloane@nwu.ac.za

Abstract. Small and Medium Enterprises in South Africa may need to adopt emerging technologies such as big data analytics to enhance growth strategies, enabling employment, creation, and meaningful contributions to economic development. This study aims to investigate big data analytics risk management factors and develop a model for managing implementation risk in small and medium enterprises. A conceptual model for managing big data analytics implementation risks in Small and Medium Enterprises is proposed based on a literature review on big data analytics implementation risks. The proposed conceptual model may provide new insights into supporting SMEs' big data analytics implementation. The overall practical contribution of this study is to assist SMEs with the big data analytics implementation risks model. Literature shows that research has been conducted on big data analytics implementation risks in SMEs.

Keywords: Big data analytics, big data analytics risk factors, SMEs.

1 Introduction

1.1 Big data analytics

Big data analytics in an increasingly digital environment represents the potential for Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) to navigate and survive in this changing environment. As such, there is growing interest in big data analytics from academia and industry [1, 2]. However, implementing data analytics projects is risky [3, 4] with project failure rates estimates running over 80% [4]. Furthermore, implementing big data analytics projects introduces additional company risks [4]. Nevertheless, despite the implementation risks and high project failure rates, big data analytics are critical in Small and Medium Enterprises. Big data analytics may be defined as the process of

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collecting and systematising massive and varied data [5, 6] and applying advanced analytic techniques [7, 8] to uncover hidden patterns [9, 5, 6, 10]. Moreover, big data analytics supports the identification of unknown correlations, market trends, customer preferences and other helpful information [11] to enhance decision-making [12, 9, 6] productivity and innovation [9]. In addition, big data analytics relies on structured and unstructured big data [10] to discover knowledge and intelligence [5, 9].

There are several benefits to using big data analytics. According to [7], big data analytics presents several benefits to companies in generating accurate business insights and understanding. Furthermore, big data analytics enables enhanced customer targeting [7], supporting the acquisition of new customers [13], markets [7] and customer retention whilst improving customer service. In addition, big data analytics empowers companies to quantify market sentiment [7]. Moreover, [12] big data analytics allows better decision-making by transforming low-value raw data into high-value information and higher product and service quality. Furthermore, big data analytics increase operational efficiencies [12, 13, 14]. As big data analytics supports business process optimisation [12], enhancing planning, forecasting and identification of root causes of cost [7], thus reducing cost [12, 6].

Big data analytics are vital in enabling competitive advantage. As big data analytics provide users with a consolidated view of data from multiple data sources [6], facilitating informed strategic direction [13], competitive differentiation through innovation and the creation of new products [13]. Furthermore, big data analytics presents new opportunities for fraud detection and risk quantification [7], enhancing revenue growth and profitability. Furthermore, big data analytics enables automated decision-making support [7]. Similarly, big data analytics enhances organisational efficiency [15, 12, 13] and speed, enabling access to refined, processed data for improved decision-making [5].

In SMEs, big data analytics represent untapped potential. According to [16], As digital technologies such as big data analytics provide new opportunities for Small and Medium Enterprises to participate in the global economy, innovate and grow [6]. The analytical potential of big data can help Small and Medium Enterprises to be innovative and engage in the global economy [17]. However, big data analytics are not sufficiently used in Small and Medium Enterprises [18]. In South Africa, about 22 200 results in big data analytics implementations within Small and Medium Enterprises [4]. Big data analytics offer substantial benefits in Small and Medium Enterprises when successfully implemented [7].

The paper bridges the gap identified in the literature on the challenges and risks of Small and Medium Enterprises to gain more insight through leveraging big data analytics. The paper's basis will help contribute to the big data analytics field within SMEs. The paper contributes to the theoretical gap by answering the research question: What is the potential conceptual model for managing big data analytics implementation risks. Furthermore, shares insightful recommendations that could assist Small and Medium Enterprises, incubators, researchers, industrial practitioners, big data providers, and governments in the big data analytics area on the challenges of the current big data analytics implementation risks [3] linking the risks management with Small Medium Enterprises Owner-manager characteristics for an enhanced approach that more that takes into account individual owner manager innovation characteristics.

To strengthen the study, the study integrated the attributes of TOE and owner manager innovation characteristics.

The contribution of the study seeks to make a theoretical and practical contribution on managing big data analytics implementation risks and generate new insights that may be of value in supporting SMEs big data analytics implementation endeavours. Furthermore, the practical insights generated from the study may be of value to SMEs, big data analytics providers, and institutions providing SMEs support services to SMEs inclusive of governments. SMEs and other organisations may use the proposed model in assessing big data analytics implementation risks and derive strategies for overcoming potential risks, reducing big data analytics projects failures. The study bridges the gap identified in the literature on the challenges of SMEs to gain more insight through leveraging BDA. The basis of the study will help to contribute to the field of BDA within SMEs.

The study contributed to the field of big data analytics. It fills the gap by developing a model for big data analytics implementation risks. Further, an insightful recommendation that could assist researchers, industrial practitioners, big data providers, and governments in big data analytics area on the challenges of the current big data analytics methods, and solutions that would alleviate these challenges has been addressed by researchers such as [12]. This study will follow a systematic research process methodology as discussed by several researchers, ensuring that the set aim will be achieved. This model will be used not only by SMEs but also by other organisations to make decisions related to big data analytics. Literature shows that research has been conducted on big data analytics implementation risks in SMEs. This study aligned the theoretical model to big data analytics implementation risks model. This study will use positivist approach which is quantitative.

Despite big data analytics' potential to support SMEs' digital transformation endeavours, and the SMEs need to use big data analytics to learn more about and value from big data [15]. SMEs face challenges implementing big data analytics managers with high project failure rates. Furthermore, one of the main challenges in using big data analytics is managing implementation risk in big data analytics projects with big data analytics, having unique risks such as the possibility of predictive model bias, that may negatively affect the organisation deploying the big analytics projects [16]. As such, the proposed research seeks to respond to calls for additional research on managing big data implementation and contributes to research on big data analytics project risk implementation.

1.2 Big data analytics risk factors

The successful implementation of big data analytics will entail overcoming big data analytics implementation risks. Technological risk factors are one of the main elements in big data analytics implementation. technological risks are one of the most critical threats due to the considerably increasing complexity of digital technologies [19]. Big data analytics implementation technological risk factors include infrastructure and development cost, data privacy and security and data quality [20]. Based on the importance and necessity of infrastructure for the effective big data application, SMEs should attach importance to increasing investment in big data related equipment and

facilities to lay a solid foundation. Big data technologies offer numerous opportunities, and its potential is undeniable. However, data scientists are facing different challenges when dealing with large data sets to dig out knowledge from such mines of information. [21], indicated that challenges exist at different levels such as data capture, storage, searching, sharing, analysis, management, and visualization. Additionally, distributed data driven application of big data technologies also face security and privacy issues. SMEs consider data security issues more serious than large firms. This is because SMEs lack the kind of environmental conditions and IT expertise that large firms enjoy [22]. SMEs should focus on improving the standardization of management, especially strengthening the management of data, improving the overall data quality. Monitor data quality by statistical process control to avoid sudden deterioration of data quality and negative impact on data or even business caused by abnormal values and provide enterprises with more comprehensive and accurate data in order to lay a solid foundation for the efficiency of big data application.

In the current era of unmatched technological advancements, the effective use of big data analytics has become a fundamental requirement for organizations and provides opportunities for managing risks to increase competitiveness and enhance performance and productivity [23]. However, implementing big data analysis entails risks so it is important that users develop deeper understanding of the risks in order to generate innovative strategies to overcome the challenges. Technological risk factors include but not limited to complexity related to data and technology, poor quality and unorganized data, technical uncertainty, privacy and cyberattack risks/security issues, scalability risks as well as minimal technological resources and infrastructure support [22]. According to the results, managers are made to understand that technological risks are the most severe risks that need to be given much more attention when organizations are seeking implementation of big data analytics. Due to infrastructure challenges in emerging economies, the choice of technology must be given serious thought in order to ensure that the right choice of technology which is compatible with the existence infrastructure is selected.

In addition to technology in implementing big data analytics, Small and Medium Enterprises would need to overcome organisational risk factors. Organisation risk factors include management support, organisational culture and resource availability [20]. Management support comprises executive sponsorship and critical stakeholder support, while organisational culture comprises a well-defined strategic vision, organisational learning culture and open and analytical organisational culture [20]. Prior studies have indicated that top-management support is a critical driver of new technology adoption [6]. However, in SMEs, owner-managers were reported to lack willingness to implement new systems [24]. Resources would address functional and systems support, team skills and competency dedicated to big data analytics [20].

In implementing big data analytics, the environmental risk factors refer to the external macro environmental conditions, including regulatory and competitive pressure [14]. Regulatory pressure refers to government policies, laws, incentives, guidelines, and industry norms affecting digitalisation [9]. Competitive pressure originates from changes in other competition [14]. Increasing big data usage among competitors could work to pressure the owners and managers to capture business analytics and intelligence to obtain and maintain a competitive market status [8].

Big data analytics implementation process may have inherent process risk factors. Big data analytics may evolve with three challenging and interrelated processes: data understanding and preparation, model building testing and evaluation and model deployment [20].

SME owner-manager characteristics may affect managing big data analytics implementation risk. The diffusion of innovation theory presents a valuable lens for examining owner-manager characteristics' influence in managing big data analytics risks. The diffusion of innovation theory is often regarded as a helpful change model for guiding technological innovation where the innovation is modified and presented in ways that meet the needs across all levels of adopters [25]. The innovators may be categorised into five categories based on the S-curve: innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards [26]. Furthermore, adopters' distributions follow a bell-shaped curve and, over time, approach normality. At the initial stage, only a few innovators are open to the new idea and adopt its use, followed by early adopters that are perceived to be opinion leaders and the early majority that adopt new ideas just before the average member of a social system [26]. The innovators' characteristics are expected to influence managing big data analytics implementation risk. Innovators are technology enthusiasts, and early adopters are visionaries, with the early majority being pragmatists [25]. Innovators are eager to try new ideas and accept an occasional setback. The innovator plays an essential role in the diffusion process of launching a new idea in the social system by importing the innovation from outside the system's boundaries. Innovators are cosmopolites and may cope with higher levels of uncertainty. The resulting distribution is an S-shaped curve when the number of individuals adopting a new idea is plotted on a cumulative frequency over time. Only a few individuals adopt the innovation each time, which can be in a year, week, or month; such are innovators [27]. Thus, innovators are most likely to proactively manage risks, accept higher risk levels, and develop contingency plans when implementing cutting-edge big data analytics technologies and methodologies to pursue potential benefits while mitigating setbacks.

Early adopters usually have higher socioeconomic status. A significant adopter incentive is paid to acceptors; individuals of the lowest socioeconomic status seem to be the most innovative [27]. Nonetheless, incentives increase the number of adopters of an innovation, and the quality of such adoption decisions may be relatively low, leading to limitations in the intended consequences of adoption. Early adopters are localities and have the most significant degree of opinion leadership. Potential adopters look to early adopters for advice and information about the innovation [28]. Change agents generally seek them to be local missionaries to speed the diffusion process. Early adopters are not too far ahead of the average individual in innovativeness [27]. Early adopters serve as role models for many other social system members. The early adopter is respected by his or her peers. Peers respect the early adopter and make rational innovation decisions [28]. So, the role of the early adopter is to decrease uncertainty about a new idea by adopting it. Relatively earlier adopters perceive trialability as more critical than do later adopters. Early adopters are most likely to take a balanced risk management approach, seeking proven results in big data analytics by conducting thorough risk assessments and implementing targeted risk mitigation strategies to minimise potential negative consequences.

The other adopters' categories are the late majority, that adopt new ideas just after the average member of the social system, and laggards, that are the last in a social

system to adopt an innovation [26]. The late majority may be called conservatives, while laggards may be referred to as sceptics [25]. The early majority adopt new ideas just before the average member of a social system. The early majority's unique position between the very early and the relatively late to adopt makes them an essential link in the diffusion process. They provide interconnectedness in the system's networks. The early majority may adopt a cautious approach to big data analytics implementation risk, preferring tried-and-tested solutions with predictable outcomes, and may utilise risk transfer mechanisms like insurance or outsourcing to minimise exposure to potential losses.

The late majority adopt new ideas just after the average member of a social system. Adoption may be both an economic necessity and the answer to increasing network pressures. Innovations are approached with a sceptical and cautious air, and the late majority does not adopt until most others in their social system have done so [3]. The late majority could take a reactive risk approach to managing risks associated with big data analytics implementation, focusing on risk mitigation measures to minimise potential negative impacts on operations and a risk management approach that may be driven by the need to comply with industry standards and regulations.

According to [27], Laggards refer to the classification method of adopters as not symmetrical in this category. Laggards take a passive, risk-avoidant approach to managing risks associated with big data analytics implementation, prioritising traditional methods and resisting change to maintain the status quo and minimise exposure to potential risks; hence, resistance to change and preference for maintaining the status quo may outweigh willingness to address the risks actively. Innovators and early adopters could be combined into a single class to achieve symmetry, but their different characteristics mark them as two distinct categories [27]. The adopter's categories are illustrated with the estimated percentage of each category in the bell-shaped curve diagram below.

Fig. 1. Diffusion of Innovation Adopter Categories [26]

1.3 Knowledge gap

Big data analytics is a growing body of knowledge. [28] highlighting a growing interest in research and application of big data analytics in organisations. A significant amount of research in big analytics is conceptual, seeking to advance knowledge in big

data analytics, such as understanding platforms, definitions and technologies [15]. Additional studies have proposed theoretical frameworks for utilising big data analytics in education [10]. Furthermore, in order to address significant big data issues, open research concerns, and various methodologies. In addition, a literature review on big data analytics studies was conducted [14] as well as a review of open challenges and techniques [12]. Additionally, theoretical research focused on prominent theories used in supply chain management using big data analytics [29]. In the previous studies, four frameworks for big data analytics were identified but only two of the frameworks were relevant to managing implementation risk [2].

Empirical research on big data analytics is developing, such as examining the difficulties in implementing big data within SMEs [17]. The effect of organisational issues on extensive data analytics adoption [12] and the significant data analytics impact on enhancing organisational performance. Furthermore, the effects of technological, organisational and environmental factors on big data analytics adoption among SMEs were examined [18].

Research is beginning to emerge on the risks associated with big data analytics, investigating the barriers facing SMEs in adopting big data analytics and proposing ways to mitigate the barriers and exploit opportunities of big data analytics [2]. The majority of studies in the field of big data analysis have been conceptual in nature, examining big data's definition, risk factors associated with methods and tools [12], as well as the analysis responsibilities that fall under big data analysis areas inside organisations [5]. The emerging empirical research on big data analytics implementation risk mostly used qualitative [12]. Furthermore recommendations are made for quantitative studies examining the theories behind big data analytics [17]. More still, research on big data analytics in the SME's context have highlighted that most SMEs are still not clear on how to analyse big data [10].

Risk implementation in SMEs have made some progress in gaining insight based on previous studies [4, 17]. Moreover, studies on strategies to overcome the risks encountered while integrating and implementing big data analytics within SMEs areas [10]. A model for managing big data analytics implementation risk in SMEs based on the literature on SMEs and big data analytics was designed.

A call for research on big data analytics implementation risk have been made which led to the development of a potential model to address the gaps. Moreover, recommendations have been made for research that takes a holistic approach to data analytics implementation, not only focusing on technology aspects [10]. Furthermore, calls have been made for research on managing big data analytics risk [18], identifying explicit data analytics risks, and developing management processes at both the project and executive levels for mitigating or eliminating data analytics project risks [4].

1.4 Methodology

This section discusses the literature review that was followed as scoping and exercise on the big data analytics implementation literature. A literature search was conducted to identify pertinent literature in managing big data analytics implementation risk, including models and frameworks. An initial Google Scholar academic database such as Science Direct, Emerald and IEEE generated 70 records, of which five records were books. Of the 65 remaining articles, one was not in English,

and 14 were removed. The remainder of the articles were analysed, of which four had proposed Risk management Frameworks. The studies in the theoretical framework, such as in [29]'s study, conclude that the scientific foundation and theoretical work that has been made regarding risk assessment and management can misguide decision-makers. More studies need to be conducted about risk management, evaluation and mitigation. To explore and obtain a more robust scientific base about how risk is handled nowadays in an organisation. Thereby contribute to establishing a more developed scientific field of risk management [29]. In addition to the literature on risk implementation, a literature search was conducted on big data analytics types, factors influencing risk management in business intelligence projects and the influence of Owner managers in managing risk.

Research is beginning to emerge on the risks associated with big data analytics, investigating the barriers facing SMEs in adopting big data analytics and proposing ways to mitigate the barriers and exploit big data analytics opportunities [2]. Moreover, recommendations have been made for research to take a holistic approach to data analytics implementation, not only focusing on technology aspects [10]. Furthermore, calls have been made for research on managing big data analytics risk [8], explicitly identifying explicit data analytics risks and developing management processes at both the project and executive levels for mitigating or eliminating data analytics project risks [4].

The study collected data from SMEs. Hence, to reach all the study participants, a survey strategy was followed whereby a measuring instrument in the form of a questionnaire with closed-ended questions was used to collect data. Participants were chosen based on their knowledge and access to the necessary information, their experience and willingness to contribute relevant information to the study. The structural equation modelling was used to determine the factors that influence big data analytics implementation and the Best Worst Method was applied to prioritize the big data analytics implementation risks [17].

1.5 Findings and Discussions

Based on the literature review, a composite TOE Technology-Organization-Environment and Diffusion of Innovation theory are selected to develop the conceptual model of big data analytics implementation risks. As the use of Technology-Organization-Environment (TOE) and DOI Diffusion of Innovation theory (DOI) models may assist researchers in examining Information Technology use in Small and Medium Enterprises [9, 30]. For instance, the Diffusion of Innovation theory model focuses on the role of technological attributes as essential for Information Technology in organisations [31]. On the other hand, the Technology-Organization-Environment framework explains the internal and external factors that may affect firms' technology [32]. Integrating the Diffusion of Innovation theory model with the Technology-Organization-Environment model may lead to a comprehensive framework managing big data analytics implementation risks in Small and Medium Enterprises. A conceptual model drawing from the literature review discussion underpinned by TOE and DOI adopter categories is proposed and illustrated in the figure below.

Fig. 2. The conceptual model

1.6 Conclusion

Despite several challenges in implementing big data analytics projects, big data analytics present untapped potential in Small and Medium Enterprises. The paper proposes a conceptual model for managing big data analytics implementation risk. The identified risks are underpinned by the TOE and DOI and categorised into five main areas: technological, organisational, environmental, process and owner-manager characteristics. Thus, the paper seeks to make a theoretical and practical contribution to managing big data analytics implementation risks and generate new insights that may be of value in supporting Small and Medium Enterprises' big data analytics implementation endeavours. Furthermore, the practical insights generated from the paper may be of value to Small and Medium Enterprises, big data analytics providers, and institutions providing Small and Medium Enterprises support services to Small and

Medium Enterprises, inclusive of governments. Small and Medium Enterprises and other organisations may use the proposed model in assessing big data analytics implementation risks and derive strategies for overcoming potential risks, subsequently reducing big data analytics implementation project failure rate. Thus enabling Small and Medium enterprises to tap into the opportunities presented by big data analytics in a dynamic and continuously changing business environment. Future research could empirically test the model and, in addition, rank the factors to provide valuable insights as to where Small and Medium Enterprises may focus efforts and scarce resources in managing big data analytics implementation risks. In addition, 2 future research could examine the identified risks and owner-manager characteristics in the context of different sectors.

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